

STUDY OF THE BACTERICIDAL EFFECT OF VARIOUS CLEANING AGENTS ON MICROBES.

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Introduction. An increase in the number of pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms in the skin microflora causes various infectious diseases. Soaps are widely used among people to prevent such unpleasant situations and have become an integral part of personal hygiene. Currently, there is no information on the bactericidal effect of soaps sold in Uzbekistan and produced in various countries (Protex, Absolut, Dettol, Safeguard, Luscan, Boro Plus, “Vesna” tar soap, Ultra-C) on bacteria. Therefore, the study of the bactericidal effect of these cleaning agents is relevant.

Purpose of the study. Study of the effect of antibacterial detergents, widely used in Uzbekistan, on microorganisms.

Materials and methods. The antibacterial and household soaps used for the study were purchased from pharmacies and perfume stores in the territory of the city of Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan. The product batch numbers, expiration dates, and the presence or absence of the manufacturer's seal were noted. Bacterial cultures (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Staphylococcus haemolyticus*, *Candida albicans* and *Escherichia coli*) isolated from patients who applied to the microbiological, virological, and immunological laboratory of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy were selected. 1 gram of each soap sample was scraped with a sterile knife and dissolved in 9 milliliters of distilled water to form stock solutions. Disks of the same size (diameter 9 mm) were cut from Whatman filter paper and sterilized in an autoclave for 15 minutes. Then the sterilized discs were immersed in soap solutions and left for 1 hour for complete impregnation. Then the discs were removed from the solutions, dried in a furnace at 25°C, and stored in sterile glass containers for further use. The antibacterial effect of the selected soaps was investigated by the agar-disk diffusion method in clinical bacterial cultures.

Results of the study. According to the results, it was found that *Staphylococcus aureus* is sensitive to Boro Plus, Safeguard, natural tar soap “Vesna”, Dettol, Absolut, and perfumed soap “Olivia”. High sensitivity to Ultra-C soap was detected in *St. haemolyticus*. Boro Plus soap also formed an inhibition zone in this bacterial culture. Among all soaps, *St. epidermidis* showed sensitivity only to Boro Plus soap. *E.coli* and *Candida albicans* cultures were found to be resistant to all tested soap types.

Conclusions. This study found that different soaps have different bactericidal effects on different bacteria. For some soaps, the test result was recorded as negative. Since the antibacterial soap Boro Plus has a higher effect compared to others, the use of this soap was found to be effective in preventing skin infections.